

MODELLING THE VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF ARTERIES USING CONSTITUENT-BASED QUASI-LINEAR VISCOELASTICITY

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SUMMARY

Arteries are known to exhibit viscoelastic mechanical properties. Given the assumption that a tissue's viscous relaxation rate is independent of the instantaneous local strain, quasi-linear viscoelasticity (QLV) is a convenient mathematical formulation to model viscoelasticity in biological soft tissues. Recent experimental work, however, suggests that the QLV assumption at tissue level may be inadequate to describe arterial viscoelasticity. A possible explanation is that arteries are heterogeneous tissues and viscoelastic properties likely differ between different arterial constituents. Hence, we propose a revised version of QLV in which the QLV assumption is made on a *constituent* (i.e., elastin and collagen) rather than on a *tissue* level to attain a deformation-dependent viscoelastic response.

Key words: *arterial biomechanics, arterial stiffness, biaxial biomechanical testing, viscoelasticity*

1 INTRODUCTION

The viscoelastic properties of arteries have long been known [1, 2]. Nevertheless, most studies on arterial mechanics focus on the quasi-static behaviour of the arterial wall (i.e., its response to very slow deformations) and model the wall as a hyperelastic material [3], neglecting viscous phenomena. Likely reasons for this simplification are the complexity of performing dynamic experiments and the difficulty of effectively modelling viscoelastic behaviour. In 1993, Fung introduced the concept of quasi-linear viscoelasticity (QLV) [5], a relatively simple approach to viscoelastic modelling. The fundamental assumption of QLV is that the viscous relaxation rate of a material is independent from the deformation state, thus allowing the definition of a relaxation function that is function of time only. Although QLV is computationally convenient, recent experimental studies have shown that it may fall short in accurately capturing the complex dynamic response of blood vessels. In particular, we showed previously that loading rate-induced wall stiffening of the mouse carotid artery was highly dependent on the level of pressure applied; being higher at high pressures than at low pressures [6]. Similarly, Franchini et al. [7] found that viscoelastic behaviour of the human aortic wall was strongly dependent on the initial deformation state. Furthermore, they found important differences in layer-specific viscoelasticity and hypothesised that such differences may arise from inter-layer differences in microstructure and composition.

This study, hence, aims to further develop the concept of QLV, by applying its formulation and assumption at a *constituent* rather than at a *tissue* level.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modelling framework

The arterial wall was assumed to be a thin cylindrical membrane. The fundamental assumption of QLV [5] allows us to introduce a relaxation function $G(t)$ that is a function of time only and that describes the relaxation of the elastic stress (i.e., the stress resulting from the instantaneous deformation of the material) following the application of a constant deformation over time. Given any deformation history mapping the transition from the unloaded configuration to the current configuration, the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff (PK) stress \mathbf{S} at any time t can then be calculated as

$$\mathbf{S}(t) = \int_0^t G(t-s) \frac{d\mathbf{S}^e(s)}{ds} ds, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{S}^e is the 2nd PK elastic stress (i.e., resulting from an instantaneous deformation) and assuming $\mathbf{S}(0) = 0$. The relaxation function used in this study was previously proposed by Fung [5]:

$$G(t) = \left[1 + \nu \left(\int_{t/\tau_2}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-m}}{m} dm - \int_{t/\tau_1}^{+\infty} \frac{e^{-m}}{m} dm \right) \right] \left[1 + \nu \ln \left(\frac{\tau_2}{\tau_1} \right) \right]^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

where ν is a dimensionless parameter and τ_1 and τ_2 are time constants ($\tau_2 > \tau_1$). A relevant feature of Eq. 2 is that, given a cyclic deformation, the hysteresis area enclosed in the resulting stress-stretch relationship is nearly constant for loading frequencies that fall in the range $1/\tau_2 - 1/\tau_1$. The choice of G was based on the empirical observation that soft biological tissues display a remarkably stable hysteresis area over a wide range of loading frequencies. The instantaneous elastic response of the arterial wall was modelled using a four-fibre family strain energy function Ψ , using an *in vivo* reference configuration and deposition stretches as proposed previously [4]. Ψ accounts for the summed contribution of a Neo-Hookean elastin matrix (Ψ_e) and four families of exponential collagen fibres with different discrete orientations (summed together in Ψ_c). While the original QLV formulation did not distinguish between individual wall constituents, our model expands on this formulation by assuming QLV at a wall constituent level; i.e., the viscoelastic response of each wall constituent is assumed independent from the deformation state but separate relaxation functions are defined for elastin (G_e) and collagen (G_c). The extra part (t_{ii}^*) of the total wall Cauchy stress in the three principal directions $i = \{\theta=\text{circumferential}, z=\text{axial}, r=\text{radial}\}$ can then be calculated as (no sum on i)

$$t_{ii}^*(t) = \left\{ \int_0^t \left[G_e(t-s) \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_e(s)}{\partial \lambda_i(s)^2} \right) + G_c(t-s) \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_c(s)}{\partial \lambda_i(s)^2} \right) \right] ds \right\} 2\lambda_i(t)^2, \quad (3)$$

with λ_i the wall stretch in direction i . As shown in Eq. 3, the proposed framework partially relaxes the standard QLV assumption, as the viscoelastic response of the arterial wall tissue becomes intrinsically dependent on the relative contribution of each wall constituents at any given deformation state.

2.2 Experimental data

The proposed modelling framework was used to capture the biaxial mechanical behaviour of the mouse carotid artery. Briefly, the artery was mounted on a custom biaxial testing set-up that allows to simultaneously subject tubular vessels to prescribed axial stretches and intraluminal pressures while continuously recording the outer diameter *via* video tracking and the axial force *via* a load cell. After opportune preconditioning, the loading protocol consisted of three blocks of tests. First, the vessel was subjected to three quasi-static inflation-deflation pressure sweeps between 10 and 180 mmHg at a rate of ~ 3 mmHg/s while being held at a constant axial stretch of 105%, 95%, and 100% of the *in vivo* axial stretch ($\hat{\lambda}_z$), respectively. Second, while keeping the axial stretch constant at $\hat{\lambda}_z$, the vessel was subjected to a sinusoidally oscillating pressure at four different frequencies $f=2.5, 5, 10,$ and 20 Hz and at three different pressure ranges: 40–80 mmHg (low), 80–120 mmHg (medium), and 120–160 mmHg (high) (i.e., dynamic testing at $4 \times 3 = 12$ f -pressure combinations). Third, the vessel was subjected to five quasi-static axial force sweeps between $F_z = 0$ N and the maximum axial force reached during the quasi-static pressure sweeps, at a constant stretch rate of 0.04 s^{-1} and while keeping a constant intraluminal pressure of 10, 60, 100, 140, and 180 mmHg, respectively. This protocol thus yields a total of 20 different biaxial testing datasets.

2.3 Parameter estimation

The proposed viscoelastic model comprises 20 model parameters: 3 for Ψ_e (one stiffness-like parameter and two deposition stretches), 11 for Ψ_c [one stiffness-like parameter, one non-linearity parameter and one deposition stretch in the fibre direction for each collagen family (note: the two diagonal families have the same parameters); one orientation angle for the diagonal collagen fibres; and one non-linearity parameter for all compressed fibres], and 3 for each of the two relaxation functions (Eq. 2). A preliminary sensitivity analysis revealed the necessity to constrain some of these parameters not to incur overfitting. Pertaining to the elastic model, elastin's deposition stretch in the axial direction was fixed to $\hat{\lambda}_z$. Further, accurate estimation of the time constants in the relaxation function G requires testing the vessel over a wide range of loading frequencies (ranging $\sim 10^{-3}$ s to $\sim 10^3$ s) to identify the frequency band in which the wall displays a relatively stable hysteresis behaviour. As this is hardly achievable experimentally, we fixed $\tau_1=10^{-2}$ s and $\tau_2=10^2$ s for both G_e and G_c . Then, the optimisation of the remaining 15 parameters was performed in three steps. First, the quasi-static data was fitted using a purely elastic model (i.e., varying the 13 unconstrained parameters of Ψ). This allowed to estimate and then fix three parameters of Ψ_c , representing the deposition stretches of the four families of collagen fibres (the two diagonal fibre families have the same deposition stretch), which were assumed to be unaffected by the viscoelastic formulation. Second, the quasi-static pressure sweep at $\hat{\lambda}_z$ and all dynamic tests (also performed at $\hat{\lambda}_z$) were fitted simultaneously using the full viscoelastic model (i.e., the 10 remaining unconstrained parameters in Ψ and a ν parameter for elastin (ν_e) and collagen (ν_c)). This was done to allow the model to capture as accurately as possible the wall behaviour at this axial stretch, thus accurately identifying the combination of ν_e and ν_c that best captures the transition from quasi-static to dynamic behaviour. Third, the remaining 10 parameters of Ψ were estimated by fitting the viscoelastic model on all quasi-static experiments.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Figure 1A–B presents the experimentally measured quasi-static pressure-diameter and circumferential stress-stretch relationships at $\hat{\lambda}_z$, as well as the 10 Hz dynamic loops at the three tested pressure ranges. Despite the slow inflation rate imposed during the quasi-static experiments, the quasi-static pressure-diameter sweep displays considerable hysteresis, suggesting that viscous effects remain non-negligible even at loading frequencies that are far below the physiological range (~ 3 vs ~ 800 mmHg/s). Figure 1C shows the ratio between dynamic (E) and quasi-static (E_{QS}) tangential elastic moduli (moduli as derived from the slope of the Cauchy stress-stretch relationships) at the three considered pressure levels. In agreement with previous findings [6, 7], the viscoelastic response of the mouse carotid artery was dependent on the deformation level, with E/E_{QS} gradually increasing from 1.03 at 80–40 mmHg to 1.31 at 160–120 mmHg.

Figure 1D–F shows the wall behaviour as captured by the proposed constituent-based QLV model. Overall, the model was able to capture well the experimental data: $R_D^2=0.98$ for the transition between quasi-static and dynamic behaviour at $\hat{\lambda}_z$ (fitting step 2) and $R_{QS}^2=0.96$ for the simultaneous fitting of all quasi-static curves (fitting step 3). Interestingly, according to the proposed model, elastin's contribution to the wall viscosity was negligible ($\nu_e = 0$). This result is explained by the fact that, experimentally, E/E_{QS} was close to 1 at 80–40 mmHg, a pressure range where the elastin response dominates the wall behaviour. Conversely, ν_c was 0.037 which, together with τ_1 and τ_2 , leads to a stress relaxation of $\sim 48\%$. As a result, as shown in Figure 1F, the proposed constituent-based QLV approach was able to capture deformation-dependent viscoelasticity at the wall level, with the modelled E/E_{QS} gradually increasing with increasing pressure when Ψ_c becomes dominant over Ψ_e . The modelled E/E_{QS} at 10 Hz was 1.00, 1.29, and 1.40 for loops at 80–40, 120–80, and 160–120 mmHg, respectively, close to the experimentally observed E/E_{QS} values of 1.03, 1.23, and 1.32.

Our model was less effective in capturing viscoelasticity-induced energy losses. This was particularly apparent for the low-pressure dynamic loop (80–40 mmHg), where the modelled hysteresis area was ~ 2.5 -fold lower than that found experimentally (583 vs 233 Pa). Conversely, for the medium- and high-pressure loops and for the quasi-static pressure sweep, differences between experimental and modelled energy losses were much smaller (118 vs 91 Pa, 19 vs 44 Pa, and 4.1 vs 3.8 kPa,

Figure 1: Experimental (A–C) and modelled (D–F) viscoelastic behaviour of the mouse carotid artery. Panels A and D show experimental (A) and modelled (D) pressure-diameter relationships under quasi-static and dynamic (loading frequency $f = 10$ Hz) loading conditions. Panels B and E present corresponding experimental and modelled circumferential Cauchy stress-stretch relationship. Panels C and F present the ratio between quasi-static (E_{QS}) and dynamic (E) tangential elastic moduli in the pressure range corresponding to each dynamic loop, for $f = 2.5, 5, 10,$ and 20 Hz.

respectively). This finding is not surprising when considering that, in the QLV formulation and, more generally, in viscoelastic theory, dynamic stiffening and hysteresis behaviour are coupled [5]. Therefore, a large hysteresis area, as observed experimentally within the low-pressure loop, can be modelled only with a considerable difference between quasi-static and dynamic slopes (stiffnesses). Such difference is not observed experimentally, suggesting that viscoelasticity *per se* is unable to capture the experimentally observed mechanical behaviour.

In conclusion, our preliminary study demonstrates the potential of constituent-based QLV to overcome the limitations of standard QLV. When applied to the mouse carotid artery, the proposed framework was able to capture the complex dynamic biaxial experimental data obtained therein.

REFERENCES

- [1] D.H. Bergel. The dynamic elastic properties of the arterial wall. *J Physiol*, 156:458–469, 1961.
- [2] R.H. Cox. A model of the dynamic mechanical properties of arteries. *J Biomech*, 5:135–152, 1972.
- [3] A. Giudici, I.B. Wilkinson, and A.W. Khir. Review of the techniques used for investigating the role elastin and collagen play in arterial wall mechanics. *IEEE Rev Biomed Eng*, 14:256–269, 2021.
- [4] C. Bellini, J. Ferruzzi, S. Roccabianca, E.S. Di Martino, and J.D. Humphrey. A microstructurally motivated model of arterial wall mechanics with mechanobiological implications. *Ann Biomed Eng*, 42:488–502, 2013.
- [5] Y.C. Fung. *Biomechanics*. 2nd Edition, Springer Science, 1993.
- [6] M.M. van der Bruggen, K.D. Reesink, P.J.M. Spronck, N. Bitsch, J. Hameleers, R.T.A. Megens, C.G. Schalkwijk, T. Delhaas, and B. Spronck. An integrated set-up for ex vivo characterisation of biaxial murine artery biomechanics under pulsatile conditions. *Sci Rep*, 11:2671, 2021.
- [7] G. Franchini, I.D. Breslavsky, G.A. Holzapfel, and M. Amabili. Viscoelastic characterization of human descending thoracic aortas under cyclic load. *Acta Biomater*, 130:291–307, 2021.